

EFFECT OF KIDNAPPING ON THE LIVELIHOOD ACTIVITIES OF ARABLE CROP FARMERS IN SOME SELECTED LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREAS OF TARABA STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study was carried out on the effects of kidnapping on livelihood activities of arable crop farmers in some selected Local Government Areas of Taraba State, Nigeria. Multistage sampling procedures were used to select one hundred and seventy arable crop farmers for the study. Frequency, percentages, mean, chi-square and logit regression were used in the analysis of the data. The result reveals 81.2% of the arable crop farmers were male, 80% were married and 68.8% had acquired one form of education or the other with a mean household size of seven people respectively. The majority (97.7%) had crop production and trading as prioritized livelihood activities. The chi-square result reveals crop production, local crop processing, marketing and distribution of agricultural produce, trading, and fishing (34.2***) were all significantly related to human abduction. Logit regression result reveals that age (0.000), and gender (0.000) were positive and statistically significant at 5% level. The result of the hypothesis tested reveals Age, gender, marital status, educational level, membership of cooperatives, household size, and extension visitation (0.41***) were all significantly related to human abduction threat. The study concluded that Human abduction is considered to be a major potential threat affecting Taraba State mostly on the part of socio-economic activities of the region. The study therefore recommended among others relevant security agencies, especially the anti-kidnapping; vigilante groups and hunters squad should be properly equipped and funded to stamp out human abduction in Taraba State.

Keywords: kidnapping, arable crop farmers, livelihood activities.

INTRODUCTION

Kidnapping is the forcible seizure, taking away and unlawful detention of a person against his/her will; it is a restriction of someone else liberty which violates the provision of freedom of movement as enshrined in the constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria, where every other law takes its cue from (Ladan and Matawalli, 2020). Kidnapping can be seen as false imprisonment in the sense that it involves the illegal confinement of individuals against his or her own will by another individual in such a way as to violate the confined individual's right to be free from the restraint of movement (Joshua and Seline, 2019).

Over the years, North East region had witnessed a serious insecurity challenge of cattle rustling and banditry which transformed into human abduction, wanton killings and ethnic bigotry, that completely distorted the social order and fabric of the various communities in the region. However, a problem, which initially appeared as localized disputes between herders and farmers over access to land, has morphed into a kidnapping posing a major threat to national and regional security. The level of rural kidnapping escalated between 2014 and 2021 attracting a lot of attention (Ajodo-Adebanjoko, 2020). The incidence of kidnapping has destabilized agricultural and socio-economic activities of the nations (Hassan and Tanko, 2023). The instability generated by kidnapping has caused an exact and substantial decrease in agricultural production (Ojo *et al.*, 2018).

The effects of kidnapping are numerous and cut across all aspects of life, especially in the

northeastern part of Nigeria (Jare and Bunu, 2021). Many rural areas in the epicenter of the kidnapping have been rendered unsafe for human habitation, pushing hundreds of thousands of farmers out of their lands. It should be noted that the bulk of the farmers in Nigeria are rural dwellers and rural areas happened to be the hardest hit areas by the kidnapping (Shettima, 2016). This has seriously affected all forms of livelihood activities including agricultural production. In a region known for its debilitating poverty, aridity, and periodic cycle of drought and famine, the kidnapping has further sown the seeds of famine (Shettima, 2016).

Kidnapping had significantly affected the agricultural production and welfare of the people around the area mostly affected by kidnapping (Madu, 2019). The activities of the kidnapper have seriously affected various fields of human endeavors that could be categorized into physical, social and economic factors (Babagana, Sani, Aliyu, and Azazi, 2018). Physically, the attacking of schools, places of worship, market structures, farmland, houses and some infrastructures like roads, bridges and electricity cables have halted developmental projects that could have a positive bearing on the lives of the entire community especially that of rural farmers (Bisong, Charles, Martins, and Barna, 2022). They could not easily move around to carry out their farming activities as well as the marketing of agricultural produce for the fear of the unknown.

Socially, the kidnappings have resulted in to increase in crime rate, a reduction in the standard of living and an increased number of refugee influxes, as well as setbacks in the

Agriculture and educational system. These have resulted in a drop in the formal and informal sectors of the economy compared to what was obtainable some years back. Economically, the kidnapping has affected market linkages between towns and cities and many businesses have closedown thereby crippling the income generating potentials of the rural farmers. These have serious bearing on the rural farmers as they cannot go on with their economic activities peacefully (Bisong, et al., 2022). Several studies have previously been conducted on the kidnapping phenomenon which include the socioeconomic implication of kidnapping and hostage-taking in Southern Nigeria, by Benjamin, Ajah and Okpan (2018), the social problem of kidnapping and its implication on social-economic development but focused on Oyo state (Inyang and Ubong, 2013). In addition, File-Muriel (2013) investigated the problem of kidnapping but focused mainly on political kidnapping.

However, from the available research works, there is little research on kidnapping in the region under consideration. It is on this basis that this research is conducted to bridge the gap this reinforces the need to assess the effects of human abduction threats on the livelihood activities of arable crop farmers in Taraba state, Nigeria. Specifically, the study describes the socio-demographic characteristics of the arable crop farmers in the study area; identifies arable crop farmers' livelihood activities, determines the relationship between human abduction threat and livelihood activities; and determines the socio-demographic factors influencing arable crop production.

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between arable crop farmers' socio-economic characteristics and human abduction threats.

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Taraba state. Taraba state lies between latitude 6°30'N and 9°36'N of the equator and longitude 9°10' and 11°50'E of the Greenwich meridian with a population of 2,294,800 (NPC, 2006), with a minimum temperature of 22.9°C and maximum temperature of 34°C. It has a land area of 54,426 km² (Adebayo and Oruonye, 2013). The state has a mean annual rainfall ranges from 800mm in the northern part of the state to over 2000mm in the southern part. Generally mean annual rainfall is less than 1000mm in the places above latitude 9° comprising Lau and Karim Lamido areas (Adebayo and Oruonye, 2013).

The population of the study comprises all arable crop farmers who are threatened by Kidnapping in Taraba state, Nigeria. Multi-stage sampling technique was used in the selection of arable crop farmers for the study. Stage one: Purposive selection of one Local Government Area each from Agricultural Development Zones I, II, III and IV due to their participation in crop production and experiencing human abduction threats. Stage two: It involved the random selection of two towns/villages from each of the selected local government areas to give a total of eight towns/villages respectively. Stage three: Random sampling was used to select one and seventy-six (176) arable crop farmers from the selected communities which were used as sample frames for the study.

Table 1: Sampling frame for the study

Zones	Local governments	Towns/Villages Selected	Respondents
Zone I	Ardo-Kola	Sunkani	25
		Mallum	25
Zone II	Gassol	Mutum-Biyu	25
		Shira	25
Zone III	Takum	Kashimbila	25
		Takum	25
Zone IV	Sardauna	Nguroje	10
		Maisamari	10
Total	4	8	176

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The data was collected with the aid of questionnaires administered to the arable crop farmers. Frequency, percentage, mean and rating scale, Chi-square were used to analyze the objective of the study while the logit regression model was used to test the hypotheses of the study.

The Logit regression model

The logit regression model is explicitly expressed as follows:

$$Y = \exp \frac{(b_0 + b_1 x_1 + b_2 x_2 \dots \dots \dots b_9 x_9)}{1 + \exp (b_0 + b_1 x_1 + b_2 x_2 \dots \dots \dots b_9 x_9)}$$

- Y = Human abduction
 $X_1 - X_9$ = Independent variables
 X_1 = Age (in years)
 X_2 = Sex (Male 1, female 0)
 X_3 = Marital status (Single 0, Married 1)
 X_4 = Farm size (Hectare)
 X_5 = Educational status (Number of years in formal schooling)
 X_6 = Membership of cooperatives (Yes 0, No 1)
 X_7 = Household size (Number of people in the household)
 X_8 = Farming experience (Number of years spent in farming)
 X_9 = Access to extension services (Yes 0, No 1)

Chi-square

Where;

r	=	Simple correlation coefficient
n	=	Sample size
y	=	Socio-economic characteristics
Y_1	=	Age (in years)
Y_2	=	Sex
Y_3	=	Marital Status
Y_4	=	Farm size (in ha)
Y_5	=	Educational level
Y_6	=	Membership of cooperative
Y_7	=	Household size
Y_8	=	Farming experience
Y_9	=	Access to extension service

Mean

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum X}{n}$$

Where;

\bar{X}	=	Mean score
\sum	=	Summation
F	=	Frequency of response mode
n	=	Likert nominal value
Nr	=	Number of response

The total score of each response was computed and the mean obtained. Mean score of 1.5 and above was regarded as a positive statement (Agreed) and the mean score less than 1.5 were regarded as a negative statement signifying disagreement with the statement

Results and Discussion

Socio-economic characteristics of the arable crop farmers

Result in Table 2 majority (81.2%) of the arable crop farmers were males. This implies that male participates more in arable crop farming, this may be as a result of manual labour practice in some aspect that requires energy. The study is in line with the findings of Adebayo and Muyanda (2020), Akler (2020), Sennuga *et al.* (2020) and Gwandi *et al.* (2021). who all reported in a separate study that a higher number of males formed majority of small holder arable crop farmers. Most (33.7%) of the farmers were within the age of 21 - 40 years with the mean age of 45 years. This implies that no much variations in the ages of crop farmers as most were young, energetic and agile to participate in every aspect of crop production activity with an increasingly and sustained labour force required. This is similar to the findings of Amare *et al.* (2020), Akkanni and Gabriel (2020) and Nnabuife (2020) who all reported an average mean age of 41 years among arable crop farmers. Majority (80%) of the farmers were married. This implies

that marriage is accustomed to the society as it is accompanied by respect and recognition. This is similar to the result of Kabaora (2020) and Konsa *et al.* (2020), who found that livelihood activities such as farming and trading were mostly carried out by married individuals to earn a better households living. Majority (68.8%) of the farmers had acquired one form of education or the other. This implies there is high level of literacy among arable crop farmers in the study area. The level of crop farmers' literacy would enhance transition by providing reliable extension services which would be easily apprehended by the literate farmers and boost productivity thereby engaging many in livelihood activities as a tool to national food security measure. Most (46.5%) of the arable crop farmer had a household size of 1-5 people. with a mean household size of seven people respectively. This implies that majority of arable crop farmers had a larger household that could supply the required farm labour for crop production activities. This study is *et al.* (2020) and Midendorf *et al.* (2021) who reported an average mean score of 6 people per small holder farmer households, implying adequate manpower for farming operations and other livelihood diversifications.

Result in Table 2 further reveals half (50%) of the farmers indicated that, they do not belong to any cooperative organization. This implies that about half of the arable crop farmers were yet to be register members of cooperatives as such could limit themselves from accessing the required extension services and other interventions to include inputs and information that could help them recover from various crop productions shocks and better their standard of living. This contradicts the findings of Balana *et al.*, (2020) and Dia *et al.*, (2020) who reported that majority of arable crop farmers participates in cooperative society. Majority (95.9%) had admitted to have no access to agricultural extension services in the study area. this shows that most of the arable crop farmers had no access to extension services and are limited to accessing required information and interventions which include among others inputs from ADPs and other government intervention platforms due to their access to low information. This corroborates the findings of Ijogu (2016), Petros *et al.*, (2017), Ganawah and Kamara (2021) who all reported that arable crop farmers had low or no available agricultural extension services in their studies

Table 2: Distribution of arable crop farmers based on Socio-economic characteristics

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Gender			
Male	138	81.2	
Female	32	18.8	
Age (years)			
21-30	15	8.8	
31-40	44	25.9	
41-50	50	29.4	
51-60	53	31.2	45
61 and above	8	4.7	
Marital Status			
Single	34	20	
Married	136	80	
Level of Education			
Non-Formal Education	53	31.2	
Primary Education	22	12.9	
Secondary Education	66	38.8	
Tertiary Education	29	17.1	
Household Size			
1-5	61	35.9	
6-10	79	46.5	
11-15	26	15.3	
16-20	2	1.2	7
21-25	2	1.2	
Farming Experience			
1-5	15	8.8	
6-10	31	18.2	
11-15	82	48.2	12
16-20	34	20.0	
21-25	8	4.7	
Membership			
Yes	85	50	
No	85	50	
Access to Extension			
Yes	7	4.1	
No	163	95.9	

Livelihood activities of arable crop farmers

The result in Table 3 shows that the majority (97.7%) of the farmers had crop production and trading as a prioritized livelihood, 93.6% had local crop processing as a livelihood activity, 89.5% had marketing and distribution of agricultural produce as a livelihood activity, 75.4% were art and local craft, 85.4% were civil service as their means of earning livelihoods, 83.0% had animal husbandry as source of livelihood, 96.5% were into cutting and selling of fuel wood while 94.2% had fishing as their livelihood activity. This implies that crop production was a major source of livelihood to respondents in the study area as such household's needs and demands were met with earnings from crop production, thereby and trading making it a bedrock of the rural households.

Tables 3 Distribution of arable crop farmers based on Livelihood activities

Activities	Yes	No
Crop production	97.7	2.3
Local crop processing	93.6	6.4
Marketing and distribution of agricultural produce	89.5	10.5
Trading (Business)	97.7	2.3
Art and local craft	75.4	24.6
Civil servant	85.4	14.6
Animal husbandry	83.	17
Cutting and selling of fuel wood	96.5	3.5
Fishing	94.2	5.8

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Relationship between human abduction threat and livelihood activities of the arable crop farmers

The entries in Table 4 show that all the selected variables Crop production, Local crop processing, marketing and distribution of agricultural produce, trading (business), and fishing (34.2***) were all significantly related to human abduction.

From this analysis, the information needed on the entire selected variable has a significant relationship to why abduction is a frequent happening in the study area. The more prominent one is known in any livelihood activity the more open is he to abduction. The alternative hypothesis (H_a) which states that there is a significant relationship between respondent socio-economic characteristics and human abduction threats is accepted while the null hypothesis states that, there is no significant relationship between respondent socio-economic characteristics and human abduction threats is rejected at 5% level of significance.

Variables	X^2	X^2	Decision rule
Crop production			
Local crop processing			
Marketing and distribution of agricultural produce	60.2	34.2***	Reject H_0
Trading (Business)			
Art and local craft			
Civil servant			
Animal husbandry			
Cutting and selling of fuelwood			
Fishing			

Tables 4: Chi-Square of Relationship between human abduction threat and livelihood act.

Variables	X^2	X^2	Decision rule
Age			
Gender			
Marital Status	0.58	0.41***	Reject H_0
Educational Level			
Membership of Cooperatives			
Household Size			
Extension Visitation			

***: Significant at 5%

NS: Not Significant

DF: Degree of Freedom 1

X^2 Calculated chi-square value

X^2 Tabulated chi-square value

Decision rule: If X^2 cal. > X^2 tab. It is Significant

Relationship between human abduction threat and livelihood activities of the arable crop farmers

Furthermore, the result of the relationship between respondents' socio-economic characteristics of arable crop farmer and abduction threat in Table shows that all the selected variables age, gender, marital status, educational level, membership of cooperative, household size, and extension visitation (0.41***) were all significantly related to human abduction threat. The information needed on the entire selected variable has a significant relationship to why abduction is a frequent happening in the study area. Married arable crop farmers are more prone to abduction and the more prominent one is known in any cooperative organization the more open is he to be abducted. The alternative hypothesis (H_a) which states that there is a significant

relationship between respondents' socio-economic characteristics of arable crop farmers and abduction threat is accepted while the null hypothesis states that, there is no significant relationship between respondents' socio-economic characteristics of arable crop farmer and abduction threat is threats is rejected at 5% level of significance.

Table 5 Relationship between respondents' socio-economic characteristics of arable crop farmer and abduction threat

***: Significant at 5%

NS: Not Significant

DF: Degree of Freedom 1

χ^2 Calculated chi-square value

χ^2 Tabulated chi-square value

Decision rule: If $\chi^2_{cal.} > \chi^2_{tab.}$ It is Significant

Logit Regression Result on the socio-demographic factors influencing arable crop production in the study area.

The empirical estimation of the logit analysis result as presented in Table 6 reveals that the coefficient of Age and gender were positive while the coefficient of education was negative and statistically significant at 5%. This implies that age, gender and education have a significant influence on arable crop. This is in agreement with the findings of (Salau, 2017) who reported that male arable farmers are more into arable crop farming than their female counterparts due to their natural features of flexibility, energy, freedom and agility (Ayoade, 2016). Similarly, Pinnar, (2021) reported that gender variations exist when it comes to arable crop farming among small household farmers; furthermore, Sheyi, (2018) found that male crop farmers were found to be much more involved in arable crop farming than their counterparts who are often domestically confined in most South-Sahara Africa.

Table 6: Logit Regression Result on the socio-demographic factors influencing arable crop production

Variable	Coefficient	Standard error	Wald	Sig.
Age	.087	.024	13.616	.000***
Gender	2.266	.643	12.417	.000***
Marital Status	.003	.002	3.562	.059
Education	-.106	.036	8.577	.003***
Membership	-.037	.587	.004	.950
Household Size	-.005	.018	.095	.758
Access to Extension	-.230	.446	.267	.605
Farming Experience	.181	.201	.813	.367
Constant	-2.960	2.944	1.011	.315

Numbers of observation	170
-2 Log likelihood	171.290 ^a
Cox and Snell R Square	.265
Nagelkerke R Square	.360883
Df	1

*** Significant at 1% level

Conclusion

The study has established that human abduction is a very serious issue of concern that affects people living in rural and urban communities drastically affecting their economic activities daily in almost all communities within the state. Despite efforts of governments to ensure that the perpetrators are captured and brought to justice. Human abduction is considered to be a major potential threat affecting Taraba State mostly on the part of socio-economic activities of the region. An increase in cases of abduction in the area has caused deplorable economic situations which have also posed farming activities in some parts of the state, thus farming as livelihood has been put to a standstill as farmers within this area find it difficult to have access to their farms as well as to get enough food crops to the market. Based on the findings of the study, therefore, the following recommendations were made:

- i. The government (particularly the Local government) should collaborate with the communities and other stakeholders to host regular community-based programs for value re-orientation among the people and by extension awaken the conscience of the people to the reality that matters of security must not be left to the government.
 - ii. Relevant security agencies, especially the anti-kidnapping, vigilante groups and hunters squads should be properly equipped and funded to stamp out human abduction in Taraba state.
 - iii. The government should put more effort into securing the lives and properties of its citizens through this they will feel an atmosphere of good governance and dividends of democracy.
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